

Clear Calot's Triangle, Cystic Duct Properly Clipped and Divided, Gallbladder Dissected and Extracted, There Is Bile Leak!!!

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Abstract

A typical complication following laparoscopic cholecystectomy is bile leak, which frequently arises from anatomical variations in the biliary system that are not identified. An interesting case of a 32-year-old woman who underwent an elective Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy for Gallbladder Adenomyomatosis. The structure of Calot's triangle was easily recognized during surgery, and the cystic artery and cystic duct were securely clipped and divided. Bile staining was seen in the gallbladder fossa after the gallbladder was removed. Bile continued to accumulate in the bed despite of irrigation of the operative bed, and the cause was found to be a leak from a tiny duct close to the fundus, most likely a duct of Luschka. An effective figure-of-eight suture with 3-0 Vicryl around the duct was used to control the leak. This case shows that immediate suture closure can be a successful treatment technique and highlights the significance of closely inspecting the operative bed post-procedure for accessory bile duct leaks.

Keywords: Biliary tree, Laparoscopic cholecystectomy, Luschka duct, bile leak

Introduction

An essential component of contemporary surgical care, Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy, introduced by Erich Muhe, is the accepted treatment for surgical diseases involving the gall bladder.¹The common intraoperative complications observed in LC were perforations of the gallbladder², bile leak, and bile duct injury, resulting in morbidity and mortality rates.³ The data showed that the trends suggest a reduction in Bile duct injury over time, but not in the mortality and morbidity rates.⁴Post-LC biliary leakage is a rare complication, with an incidence of less than 2% in most published studies.⁵

Five forms of laparoscopic biliary tract injuries are distinguished by the Strasberg classification system. In type A, there is a bile leak from the liver bed or cystic duct, but no additional damage. The term "type B" describes partial obstruction of the biliary tree, which frequently affects an aberrant right hepatic duct. Types C, D, and E comprise bile leaks from aberrant ducts that do not communicate with the main bile duct, lateral injuries without loss of continuity, and circumferential injuries with loss of continuity, respectively. The Strasberg type A categorization system includes sub vesical bile ducts (SVBD), a common anatomic variant of the biliary tree with frequent clinical and surgical ramifications. After the cystic duct bile leaks, the second most common cause of a small bile leak is damage to the sub vesical bile duct (SVBD).⁶The bile leak from SVBD is usually modest and heals completely on its own without the need for invasive or non-invasive treatments.⁶The duct of Luschka or sub vesical bile ducts (SVBD) or supplementary bile ducts are common sources of biliary leakage, which is typically treated conservatively and closely monitored. However, leakage brought on by a main bile duct lesion needs to be treated right away by a qualified and experienced surgeon.⁵Although titanium clips are still the most common method of anchoring the cystic duct, absorbable clips and suturing are other good options for bile leak during laparoscopic cholecystectomy.⁷The invasive management of biliary tract injury includes percutaneous drainage, ERCP, and surgical exploration.

The objective of this article is to describe a case of bile leak arising from sub vesical ducts during a Laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Case report

We describe an interesting case of a 32-year-old woman who complained of persistent pain in the right upper quadrant. There was no indication of gallstones or ductal dilatation,

and imaging tests such as abdominal ultrasonography and MRI showed characteristics compatible with Gallbladder Adenomyomatosis. The patient underwent a Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy as an elective procedure. The pneumoperitoneum was maintained at 12 mmHg after a sub-umbilical incision was made, and the abdomen was explored to reach the gallbladder.

During surgery, the critical view of safety was achieved, and the anatomy of the Calot's triangle was well visualized. The gallbladder was separated from the liver bed and extracted via the epigastric port (in an endobag) after the cystic duct and artery were cut and split.

Figure 1: Bile leak identified from the duct of Luschka (Laparoscopic view)

Bile stains in the gallbladder fossa were discovered during the surgical field assessment. Bile accumulated in the operating field despite continuous irrigation and suctioning, which raised the possibility of a bile leak. After closer examination, it was discovered that the leak was originating from a tiny duct close to the fundus region of the gallbladder, which is compatible with a duct of Luschka, an accessory sub vesical bile duct.

Figure 2: Bile leak sutured (Laparoscopic view)

A figure-of-eight suture with 3-0 Vicryl at the area of the duct/leak was planned to handle the leak. Vicryl, 3 – 0 size, an absorbable braided suture, was chosen after the bile leak location had been cleaned and identified to perform a figure-of-eight suture. A crossing loop that resembled the number eight was created by inserting the needle into one side of the duct opening at a 90° angle, exiting on the opposite side, and then reintroducing it either proximally or distally to the original exit point and the knot was tied tightly, laparoscopically.

A reassessment of the surgical field following suturing revealed no more bile leakage. As a precaution, a drain was inserted into Morrison's pouch. The patient was extubated and moved to recovery in a stable state after the port sites were closed as usual. On the second postoperative day, the drain was removed, and the recovery process was uneventful. On the fifth day, the patient was discharged without showing any symptoms of infection or bile

leakage. The histopathology revealed Adenomyomatosis without any indication of malignancy.

Discussion

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy, which was once a time-consuming innovation, has become the preferred method for gallbladder diseases and is now a common, day-case procedure.⁸

Even though the biliary tree usually follows portal system segmentation, approximately half of people have normal anatomy; therefore, understanding its variances is essential to choosing the best surgical strategy and lowering the risk of complications.⁹ Hubert von Luschka originally defined the Luschka duct in 1863. He defined it as a subvesical duct that branches off the right or main hepatic ducts, extends in the gallbladder's posterior wall's submucosa, is unconnected to the lumen, does not drain any liver parenchyma, and ends blindly in its distal portions.¹⁰ The subvesical bile ducts, commonly termed the duct of Luschka or accessory duct, are significant and could be damaged during hepatic and gallbladder procedures. Although there was a lot of variety, these ducts' origin and drainage were mostly restricted to the liver's right lobe. The subvesical ducts had an average diameter of 2 mm, with a range of 1 to 18 mm. Hepaticocholecystic ducts, superficial segmental and sectorial ducts, intercommunicating accessory ducts, and aberrant bile ducts are among the different types of subvesical bile ducts that are part of the biliary system of the right hepatic lobe. Small aberrant ducts are difficult to identify or diagnose intraoperatively or postoperatively because they frequently go undetected on imaging and may not cause clinically significant bile leakage when wounded during surgery. As a result, the true prevalence of these ducts is probably underreported.¹¹

Our case report described the bile leak originating from the subvesical bile duct (SVBD), and the occurrence of leaks from SVBD may be caused by a number of factors, including tissue inflammation, inadequate surgical field visibility due to adhesions, surgical skill, and an improper dissection plane.⁶ Li X et al¹² observed similar results, emphasizing the use of indocyanine green (ICG) fluorescence imaging to detect intraoperative bile leaks, especially in complicated situations with extensive adhesions and a thickened cystic duct. In their instance, the intraoperative bile leak locations were successfully controlled by the use of laparoscopic clips. A surgical bile leak from the duct of Luschka in a young female patient

was successfully treated by endoscopic sphincterotomy and the implantation of a double pigtail biliary stent, according to Muleta J et al.¹³ When bile leaks are diagnosed postoperatively and the patient is hemodynamically stable, this minimally invasive method provides a useful alternative for conservative management. A prospective population-based study was out in Iran by Abbas A K et al¹⁴ offers a more comprehensive view of the prevalence of biliary leakage. Bile leakage occurred in 1.75% of 968 cholecystectomies (657 laparoscopic and 311 open). Notably, the incidence of bile leak from minor ducts, including the duct of Luschka and gallbladder bed, was 1.13%. While a small percentage of these instances needed surgical intervention, such as primary duct repair or hepaticojejunostomy, the majority (70.58%) of these cases resolved with conservative care.

A safe laparoscopic cholecystectomy can be guided by a ten-point strategy that takes into account the visible intra-abdominal anatomy. A clear Calot's triangle (2), partial clearance of the cholecystic plate (2), the appearance of an "elephant head," the visualization of the common bile duct (3 points), dissection above the Rouviere sulcus (1), and the identification of only two structures entering the gallbladder—the cystic duct and artery (1) are important components. Low safety is indicated by scores of 1-4, equivocal by scores of 5-7, and a safe cholecystectomy is indicated by scores of 8-10.¹⁵ A multimodal approach combining surgical expertise, anatomical understanding, and good intraoperative judgment is necessary for a safe cholecystectomy. Achieving the critical view of safety, using energy devices carefully, and retracting the gallbladder correctly are crucial.¹⁶

Laparoscopic suturing of the leaking duct, whether it be a cystic duct stump or an auxiliary duct of Luschka, is required if the location of the bile leak is known but cannot be controlled by laparoscopic clips. Due to the unusual knot-tying angles and the possibility of sutures severing the delicate liver tissue, this can be technically difficult.¹⁷ Every kind of suture has distinct mechanical characteristics and causes various tissue reactions; the best suture material is non-traumatic, has low levels of inflammation, and absorbs quickly enough to avoid anastomotic collapse, particularly in cases of delayed healing.¹⁸ In our case report, we used absorbable Vicryl suture material (polyglactin 910), and the suturing was done by the figure-of-eight method. Since it increases tissue support and lowers the possibility of the suture pulling through, the "Figure of 8" suture is especially helpful in regions of the wound where there is a lot of tension around the tissue planes. A figure-of-eight suture is a type of

specialty stitching that creates a loop pattern that resembles the number "8" or an infinity sign. It is used to secure tissues, stop bleeding, and seal deep wounds.

During cholecystectomy, our case study highlights the significance of identifying anatomical variations like the SVBD. Even though they are rare, damage to these ducts can result in postoperative morbidity. Preventing such injuries requires careful dissection in the appropriate anatomical plane, sufficient exposure, and intraoperative attention. Additionally, using intraoperative adjuncts such as cholangiography or ICG fluorescence may help detect abnormal biliary anatomy, particularly in difficult patients.

Although preoperative radiological imaging can help detect anatomical differences, intraoperative attention to detail is still required. Before closure, the gallbladder fossa should be closely examined by surgeons for any unexpected bile leaks. A figure-of-eight suture with 3-0 Vicryl is an absorbable and efficient method for tight closure when tiny leaks are found, especially from small ducts like the duct of Luschka. This technique reduces the risk of postoperative problems.

Conclusion

In conclusion, since rare sources—like subvesical or accessory bile ducts—account for about 10% of leaks, a comprehensive final evaluation for bile leaks is crucial at the end of a laparoscopic cholecystectomy. Although preoperative radiological imaging might help detect anatomical variations, intraoperative attention to detail is still crucial. In order to detect any unexpected bile leakage, surgeons should closely inspect the gallbladder fossa. A figure-of-eight suture with 3-0 Vicryl is a dependable and efficient way to ensure secure closure and avoid postoperative difficulties when such leaks are found, especially from small ducts like the duct of Luschka.

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